

A Call for Increased Focus on Reproductive Health within Lab Safety Culture

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ABSTRACT: The approach to reproductive health and safety in academic laboratories requires increased focus and a shift in paradigm. Our analysis of the current guidance from more than 100 academic institutions' Chemical Hygiene Plans (CHPs) indicates that the burden to implement laboratory reproductive health and safety practices is often placed on those already pregnant or planning conception. We also found inconsistencies in the classification of potential reproductive toxins by resources generally considered to be authoritative, adding further confusion. In the interest of human health and safe laboratory practice, we suggest straightforward changes that institutions and individual laboratories can make to address these present deficiencies: Provide consistent and clear information to laboratory researchers about reproductive health and normalize the discussion of reproductive health among all researchers. Doing so will promote safer and more inclusive laboratory environments.

Laboratory safety has received increased attention in recent years, evidenced by the declaration of safety as a core value by the American Chemical Society, and subsequent publication of the dedicated chemical safety journal, *ACS Chemical Health and Safety*.¹ Reports investigating the root cause of safety incidents conclude that a common underlying cause is systemic failure to provide researchers with the resources to properly assess and mitigate risks.²⁻⁴ With an increase in focus on inclusion within chemistry, reproductive health safety should receive increased attention. When reproductive toxins are not handled with proper care within laboratory settings, it can lead to exposure of people that do not know they are pregnant and people undergoing spermatogenesis, as well as bioaccumulation of these toxins and chemical transmission via toxic compounds remaining on lab clothes that are worn home.⁵ Unintended exposure to reproductive toxins can lead to serious negative outcomes for all individuals. Exposure of laboratory workers to reproductive toxins can lead to infertility, reduced fertility and genetic damage to germ cells.⁵⁻⁷ Specifically, genetic damage to sperm can lead to pre-term birth, low birth weight, as well as central nervous system malformation in the fetus. Exposure to reproductive toxins during pregnancy can lead to transmission of chemicals through the placenta which can cause stillbirth, spontaneous abortion, as well as diseases or congenital abnormalities in the fetus.^{5,7} During lactation, exposure to reproductive toxins can transmit these chemicals to the child via human milk.⁵ The period encompassing planned or unplanned conception, pregnancy, and lactation amounts to years during which individuals need heightened protection from reproductive toxins. We believe that Chemical Hygiene Plans (CHPs) could serve as an important resource to provide guidance for laboratory workers on the identification of potential reproductive toxins in the workplace.

In this perspective, we evaluate the information provided by CHPs pertaining to reproductive health for university laboratory workers. Generally speaking, we find that the instruction on reproductive health safety in CHPs is absent or minimal, often puts the onus on the pregnant person or person planning to conceive to identify and minimize exposure to reproductive toxins, and generally provides non-private resources or a wide range of recommended resources with no guidance on how to use each one. After this assessment, we evaluate three external resources commonly recommended by CHPs: Safety Data Sheets (SDSs), the NIOSH Pocket Guide (NPG), and the Proposition 65 list (Prop. 65). We then compare how these sources classify chemicals listed as reproductive toxins within CHPs. Finally, we recommend straightforward changes within CHPs and laboratory-level discussions that will lead to improved guidance for reproductive safety of laboratory workers.

A way of providing sufficient protection from occupational hazards is to implement a universal or *unified protection* safety model in which all workers follow the recommended guidelines for protection of the group which is most sensitive to chemical exposure.⁶ An alternative, individualistic safety model, *differentiated protection*,^{6,8} aims to protect the sensitive group by reducing only the exposure of that group. In the context of reproductive health safety, an example of unified protection is ensuring that *all individuals* identify substances in their work as possible reproductive toxins and handle these substances accordingly. An example of differentiated protection would be removal of a pregnant worker from the lab environment to minimize their exposure to reproductive toxins. Differentiated protection has been shown to provide insufficient protection from reproductive toxins in the following situations: unplanned conception, bioaccumulation effects, and when pregnancy is not immediately known.⁶ Laboratory safety guidelines

should protect the reproductive health of all workers by implementing a unified protection safety model in which all take care to control and minimize exposures to reproductive toxins.

A first step towards implementing a unified protection safety model is to effectively communicate that the risk of reproductive toxin exposure within laboratories affects everyone. To evaluate the current messages pertaining to reproductive health that university laboratory workers are receiving, we elected to assess the guidance in university CHPs. Under OSHA's Laboratory Standard, it is recommended that all laboratories using hazardous chemicals inform laboratory workers of chemical dangers and safe-handling practices in a safety manual known as the CHP.⁹ CHPs could serve as a first resource that a laboratory worker references to begin research on reproductive toxin exposure if they are developed to provide thorough guidance on practical aspects of identifying reproductive toxins. To obtain a representative sample of university-level CHPs, we reviewed the CHPs available in 2020 by the 100 top-ranking US graduate chemistry programs¹⁰ for their discussion of reproductive health safety.¹¹ We concluded that the identification of reproductive toxins is nuanced, and that university CHPs vary in the quality of guidance that they provide to researchers for the assessment of risk of exposure to reproductive toxins. Additionally, we found that discussion of reproductive health within university CHPs generally follows a differentiated safety model by specifically advising pregnant workers or workers planning conception to identify and mitigate exposure to reproductive toxins.

While assessing reproductive health guidance, we observed that some CHPs lacked sufficient discussion of reproductive health safety. We searched for the Top 100 (105) CHPs using a Google search for "[school name] chemical hygiene plan" and found that 87 appeared within the first page of results, 6 were found after further searching, and 12 were not found at all. This led to the inclusion of 93 university CHPs in our assessment. Of the 93 CHPs assessed, only 31 indicated a section on reproductive health safety within the Table of Contents, and only 54 mentioned "pregnan[cy][t]"¹² or "male [reproductive health]" (or both) anywhere in the document.¹³ We view the lack of a reproductive health section within some CHPs as a shortcoming of reproductive health safety guidance in the academic research setting. We believe that all CHPs should contain discussions pertaining to reproductive health to further normalize this topic as an important laboratory safety principle.

In many cases, the language used in CHPs that do include sections on reproductive health implies that reproductive health only affects certain groups, such as pregnant workers or workers planning conception. In our evaluation of 93 CHPs, 17 only mentioned female reproductive health, 9 only mentioned male reproductive health, and 28 mentioned both female and male reproductive health. The mention of only one type of reproductive health in the absence of another suggests that this sensitive group should take on the responsibility of identifying reproductive health risks as well as creating a safe work environment. Unfortunately, this is an unproductive way of protecting individuals from exposure to reproductive toxins and could perpetuate unequal working environments.⁶ It is crucial that language used within CHPs clearly communicates that safety pertaining to reproductive health affects everyone and thus promotes an inclusive safety culture.

Next, we evaluated how CHPs inform laboratory workers to utilize resources for the identification of

reproductive toxins. Many CHPs recommended that laboratory workers seek advice from the Environmental Health and Safety office, Principal Investigator, or Primary Care Physician. While these resources are indispensable, some laboratory workers may hesitate to take advantage of these resources.¹⁴ For example, the individual could feel that engaging in this discussion would imply to their supervisor that they are planning conception, or they may fear the highly personal nature of the conversation. Due to the private nature of reproductive health, CHPs should inform laboratory workers about useful discreet resources which they can consult for the identification of reproductive toxins. Improving access to discreet resources should make reproductive health safety guidance available to a broader audience. Our review of CHPs revealed that the discreet resources most commonly recommended by CHPs include SDSs, NPG, and Prop. 65; these resources are open access and provide reproductive health safety guidance without the need for discussion with another individual.

In 48 of the CHPs assessed we found a list of specific examples of reproductive toxins. We compiled a list of all compounds mentioned by CHPs as examples of reproductive toxins, which resulted in 1,087 unique chemicals. Lead and carbon disulfide were the two most commonly listed chemicals, and were given as examples in 23 CHPs. Only 11 CHPs provided a literature reference for the examples, so we decided to carry out our own assessment by investigating how chemicals listed by at least five unique CHPs are classified by SDSs, NPG, and Prop. 65.¹⁵ This assessment revealed inconsistencies in the way these compounds are classified.¹⁵⁻¹⁷ Our findings are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The classification by SDSs, NPG, and Prop. 65 of compounds listed as reproductive toxins within 5 or more CHPs.

Surprisingly, only 63, 26, and 67 of compounds listed by CHPs as examples of reproductive toxins were classified as reproductive toxins within their respective SDS, NPG, or Prop. 65 entry. Of the 107 compound classifications assessed, only 26 were classified in the same way by all three. Table 1 displays the 14 most commonly reported reproductive toxins within CHPs as well as their classification within their respective SDS, NPG, and Prop. 65 entry. The inconsistencies between classifications of these compounds by various sources provides unclear guidance to laboratory workers on the identification of potential reproductive toxins

Table 1. The 14 chemicals most commonly listed as examples of reproductive toxins within university CHPs and their reproductive toxicity classification by SDSs, NPG, and Prop. 65.

CAS	Chemical Name ^a	Occurrence in CHPs	Reproductive Information ^b		
			SDS	NPG	Prop. 65
7439-92-1	lead	23			
75-15-0	carbon disulfide	23			
108-88-3	toluene	22			
71-43-2	benzene	20			
75-21-8	ethylene oxide	20			
75-01-4	vinyl chloride	18			
96-12-8	1,2-dibromo-3-chloropropane	18			
7440-43-9	cadmium	16			
75-12-7	formamide	16			
109-86-4	ethylene glycol monomethyl ether	15			
1330-20-7	xylene	14			
50-00-0	formaldehyde	13			
50-18-0	cyclophosphamide	13			
67-66-3	chloroform	13			

^aIn total, 1,087 unique reproductive toxins were listed across 93 CHPs, of which 107 compounds were listed in 5 or more CHPs. The compounds in this table are the top 14 examples. ^b Consistent with categorization in Figure 1, blue = classified as a reproductive toxin, orange = no reproductive toxin information available for this compound, green = compound is not listed on this source.

To better understand why the classification of compounds as reproductive toxins differs between sources, we investigated the authorship and sources of information for the

content provided in CHPs, SDSs, NPG, and Prop. 65. Table 2 highlights the general similarities and difference between these four resources.¹⁸⁻²²

Table 2. Comparison of resources available to laboratory workers containing information on reproductive health safety or identification of reproductive toxins in laboratories.¹⁶⁻²²

	Chemical Hygiene Plan (CHP)	Safety Data Sheet (SDS)	NIOSH Pocket Guide (NPG)	Proposition 65 List (Prop. 65)
General description of source	safety manuals that inform laboratory workers of chemical dangers as well as proper workplace safety practices	a source that contains information relating to occupational safety and health for commercially available chemicals	a guide which provides general industrial hygiene information for hundreds of chemicals/classes	a list which informs Californians of carcinogens and reproductive toxins
Is this a required source? If so, by whom?	yes, OSHA	yes, OSHA	not required, maintained by CDC	yes, State of CA
Who writes this?	employer (university)	manufacturer/distributor of the chemical, no legal requirement for authorship	Contractors and personnel from various divisions within NIOSH and OSHA	a team of scientists appointed by the governor of CA
What classifies as a reproductive toxin?	discretion of author	discretion of author based on OSHA guidelines for hazard identification and available literature and data concerning the chemical in question	compounds for which an REL or PEL has been assigned, based on NIOSH policy documents and references within industrial hygiene, occupational medicine, toxicology, and analytical chemistry	compounds known by the state of CA to cause reproductive harm, based on current labor code, states qualified experts, authoritative bodies, and formally required to be labeled
How often is this source revised?	when there is an updated requirement by OSHA (most recently 2013)	within 3 months of new and significant information regarding hazard or ways to protect against hazards, also if there is an audit	periodically to reflect new data regarding the toxicity of various substances and any changes in exposure standards or recommendations	annually

These resources have different merits when viewed through the lens of reproductive health safety. We found that the main advantage of CHPs and SDSs is availability. Each is generally available in all university labs and for all commercially available chemicals, respectively. The main drawback for these two documents is their lack of transparency regarding references and authorship. Each university or chemical supplier is responsible for producing their respective CHP or SDSs. Differences in authorship is a possible source of inconsistency which can lead to different interpretations of hazards. For example, when comparing SDSs from different chemical suppliers for *N*-nitrosodimethylamine and 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid, we find that some companies identify reproductive hazards while others do not (Table 3).²³⁻²⁷ A third example with hexafluoroacetone illustrates how different hydrates of the same molecule contain different reproductive hazard information.²⁸⁻²⁹ SDSs from different chemical suppliers differ in the information they provide due to differences in literature and

data retrieval and interpretation of information by the author.²⁰ Interestingly, an SDS may contain an H340 or H360 hazard statement in Section 2: Hazards Identification but lack a discussion of reproductive toxicity in Section 11: Toxicological Information (or vice versa, Table 3). Again, these differences can be attributed to the author's interpretation of guidelines for hazard identification. We present this information to illustrate how a laboratory worker may easily feel overwhelmed or confused in their attempt to identify reproductive toxins. As described in Prudent Practices in the Laboratory, SDSs remain "the best single source for the purpose of evaluating the hazards and assessing the risks of chemical substances". Prudent Practices also highlighting the following important limitations of SDSs: variation in quality depending on chemical supplier, differences in toxicity due to morphology or experimental scale, and overly inclusive lists of hazards which distract from those most likely to cause harm.³⁰

Table 3. Comparison of reproductive health hazard information from different SDSs.

Chemical Substance	SDS Source	SECTION 2: Hazard Identification	GHS Pictograms ³¹	SECTION 11: Toxicological information
	Germ cell mutagenicity - Reproductive toxicity -			
	Supplier 2	Germ cell mutagenicity Category 1B Reproductive toxicity Category 2 May cause genetic defects Suspected of damaging fertility or the unborn child		Germ cell mutagenicity: mmo-sat 10 mmol/L (-S9) mmo-sat 50 uL/plate (+S9) msc-hmn-lym 14 mmol/L Reproductive toxicity: orl-mus TDLo: 1940 ug/kg (75D pre/1-22D preg) orl-rat TDLo: 20 mg/kg (20D preg)
	Germ cell mutagenicity No data available Reproductive toxicity Laboratory experiments have shown teratogenic effects. No data available.			
	Supplier 2	Toxic to Reproduction [Category 2] Suspected of damaging fertility or the unborn child		Germ cell mutagenicity dni-ham-ovr 1 mmol/L sce-hmn-lym 10 mg/L mmo-sat 250 ug/plate (-S9) Reproductive toxicity orl-rat TDLo: 220 ug/kg (1-22D preg) orl-rat TDLo: 500 mg/kg (6-15D preg)
	Supplier 3	-		Mutagenic Effects No information available Reproductive Effects No information available Developmental Effects No information available Teratogenicity No information available
	Germ cell mutagenicity Test Type: Ames test Test system: Salmonella typhimurium Result: negative Remarks: (National Toxicology Program) Reproductive Toxicity No data available			
	Supplier 1 Trihydrate x = 3	Reproductive toxicity (Category 2), H361 Suspected of damaging fertility or the unborn child		Germ cell mutagenicity No data available Reproductive toxicity Possible risk of congenital malformation in the fetus. Suspected human reproductive toxicant. No data available

NPG and Prop. 65 communicate that their information is obtained from scientifically credible sources and that these documents are written by experts in the field. Importantly, NPG and Prop. 65 differ in their inclusivity: NPG is exclusive (only includes chemicals that report PELs and RELs) while Prop. 65 is inclusive (includes all potential reproductive toxins). Prop. 65 stands out in the frequency with which it is revised (annually). SDSs, NPG, and Prop. 65 all contain valuable information which should guide researchers in the identification of chemical reproductive toxins. CHPs should communicate the utility of these resources while also highlighting the important differences and the information one should expect to obtain from each source.

In conclusion, we have highlighted opportunities for improvement of reproductive health safety guidance provided to university laboratory workers by laboratory CHPs. We recommend the following straightforward changes to CHPs. First, we recommend that all CHPs include a dedicated section on reproductive health safety. Within this section, the language should communicate that *all laboratory workers* are responsible for safe handling of any potential reproductive toxins. The section should also include recommended resources for laboratory workers to consult for the identification of potential reproductive toxins in their work. Each recommended resource should include an explanation of how it is most effectively utilized. For example, the CHP should suggest NPG and Prop. 65 as reputable resources, and clearly explain the differences between and advantages of each. CHPs should inform laboratory workers that if a compound is not listed as a reproductive toxin within a CHP or SDS, this does not necessarily exclude it as a potential reproductive toxin. While some of the CHPs met many of these criteria, others did not. All laboratory workers need to hear the same message that reproductive health affects everyone.

Second, we recommend that all laboratories engage in discussions pertaining to reproductive health. We believe this will help shift the current culture away from a differentiated protection safety model. Specifically, incorporating discussions about reproductive health safety at laboratory group meetings can normalize this topic. The more laboratories are able to discuss reproductive health as a universal safety issue, and create safety plans that will protect everyone, the easier and more habitual these changes will become. Thus, we must always continue to learn and adapt our behaviors within laboratory settings, which begins with conversations between laboratory colleagues.

We believe the implementation of these changes will lead to the promotion of more inclusive safety models. This type of shift in laboratory safety culture should ultimately provide improved protection for all laboratory workers from reproductive toxins.

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ABBREVIATIONS

CHP Chemical Hygiene Plan; SDS Safety Data Sheet; NPG NIOSH Pocket Guide; Prop. 65 Proposition 65 list; PEL Permissible Exposure Limit; REL Recommended Exposure Limit; CDC Center for Disease Control and Prevention; OSHA Occupational Safety and Health Administration; NIOSH National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health; CA California.

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(12) For simplification, we used pregnan[t][cy] as a key word to identify female reproductive health within CHPs. We understand that not all pregnant people identify as female, and not all males undergo spermatogenesis.

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